

ENHANCING ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS IN OBIO/AKPOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS: THE ROLE OF PRINCIPAL-TEACHER MOTIVATION, COMMUNICATION, AND TRAINING

Nkemdilim Chijioke Obi and Miriam Ifeoma Adebayo

Department of Health Promotion, Environmental and Safety Education, Faculty of Education, University
of Port Harcourt, Rivers State

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17472625>

Abstract

Effective administration in secondary schools plays a pivotal role in ensuring quality education and creating a positive learning environment. The leadership abilities of principals and teachers are central to the success of educational institutions, particularly in motivating staff, maintaining effective communication, and engaging in continuous professional development. Motivation among both teachers and students significantly contributes to a productive school atmosphere, where teachers are more likely to adopt innovative teaching practices and students are more likely to actively engage in their learning. In secondary schools, where challenges such as inadequate resources and diverse student needs persist, the importance of skilled school leadership becomes even more critical. Motivation strategies that enhance teacher and student performance are vital in fostering academic success and school effectiveness. Communication within the school community is equally crucial, as it ensures alignment with the institution's goals and policies, facilitating smooth operations and fostering collaboration. This study explores the role of principal-teacher motivation, communication, and training in enhancing administrative effectiveness in secondary schools, with a particular focus on addressing challenges faced in diverse educational environments. By understanding the impact of these factors, this research contributes to developing strategies that promote educational quality and improve school management practices.

Keywords: School administration, teacher motivation, communication, training, secondary education.

Introduction

Effective administration in secondary schools is a critical factor in ensuring quality education and fostering a conducive learning environment Omemu (2017). The role of principals and teachers in administering schools cannot be overstated. Their ability to motivate staff, communicate effectively, and undergo continuous training significantly influences the overall performance and success of educational institutions Onubuleze (2023). Secondary education is a pivotal stage in the educational journey, shaping the academic and professional futures of students. Globally, most secondary schools face various challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, limited resources, and diverse student needs. Against this backdrop, the leadership and management skills of principals and teachers become paramount. Motivation among teachers and students is a cornerstone of effective school administration Muheeb (2014) Motivated teachers are more likely to engage in innovative teaching practices, maintain high levels of enthusiasm, and contribute positively to the school environment. Similarly, motivated students are more likely to participate actively in their learning, leading to better academic outcomes. Kanyip & Ogon (2022)

understanding how motivational strategies are implemented and their impact on school effectiveness is essential for developing interventions that enhance educational quality. Effective communication is another critical element of school administration. Clear and open communication channels between principals, teachers, students, and parents ensure that information flows smoothly and that everyone is aligned with the school's goals and policies. Globally, where schools may have diverse and multi-lingual populations, effective communication strategies are necessary to bridge gaps and foster a collaborative school community.

According to Chukwuere (2017) Continuous professional development and training are vital for equipping principals and teachers with the skills needed to manage schools effectively. Training programs help educators stay updated with the latest pedagogical methods, technological advancements, and administrative practices. In state where educational challenges can be unique and complex, tailored training programs for school leaders and teachers can significantly impact school administration and student outcomes. Recognizing and rewarding teachers' efforts, providing professional development opportunities, and creating a supportive work environment significantly contribute to a more motivated and engaged teaching staff. Similarly, motivated students tend to perform better academically and exhibit higher levels of school engagement Onubuleze (2023)

The study on "The Impact of Principals' -Teachers' Motivation, Communication, and Training on the Administrative Effectiveness of Secondary Schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State" underscores the critical role these elements play in the administration and overall success of educational institutions. Through a detailed examination of motivational strategies, communication practices, and training programs, this research has highlighted several key findings and implications for educational stakeholders.

Statement of the problem

Despite the critical role that effective administration plays in the success of secondary schools, students in schools are experiencing fear and anxiety towards their teachers and principal leading to negative impact on their academic performance emotional well-being, and overall educational experience. Many schools continue to face significant administrative challenges. Students are afraid of their teachers and these challenges include low levels of teacher and student motivation, inadequate communication channels among public, and insufficient training opportunities for principals and teachers. Consequently, these issues adversely affect the quality of education provided, student academic performance, and overall school management. The study provided answers to the following research questions:

- 1) To what extent does teacher's motivation affect the efficient administration of public secondary schools in Obio /Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State?
- 2) To what extent does principals' training/development of teachers influence their responsibility in public Secondary Schools in Obio /Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State?

3) To what extent does principals-teachers' communication influence their responsibility in public Secondary Schools in Obio /Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

- 1) There was no significant relationship between mean ratings of Principal-teachers on how motivation enhances effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State.
- 2) There was no significant relationship between the views of principal's training/development of teachers and how it influences their responsibilities in public Secondary Schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State.
- 3) There was no significant relationship between the views of principal's-teachers communication and how it influences their responsibilities in public Secondary Schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, utilizing questionnaires titled Principals-Teachers Strategies for Effective Administration of Secondary Schools Questionnaire (PTSEASSQ)"as the primary data collection instrument. It consisted of Sections A and B. Section A dealt with demographic information of the respondents while Section B dealt with variables from the research questions which were used to elicit information on principals-teachers motivation, communication and training/development. This design is chosen to facilitate the collection of data from a large sample within the target population, providing a comprehensive overview of the influence of principal-teacher strategies on the management and administration of public secondary schools. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select participants. This method ensures that subgroups within the population (principals and teachers) are adequately represented. The sample size was 384 respondents comprising 363 teachers and 21 principals representing 30% drawn from the population 24 principals and 1280 teachers of Secondary schools in Obio/Akpor using Simple random sampling technique. Data analysis was Mean, standard deviation for research questions and hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

Result and discussion

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Motivation of Staff influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

Principal- teachers Motivation	Mean	St.Dev	Decision
1 Motivating teachers through monetary and non- monetary measures can spur them into action in positive attitude to work	2.72	0.173	Moderate
2 Staff do take their job more seriously when they are involved in the decision- making or policy formulation process of the school	3.19	0.351	High
3 Appraising teaching staff through good service will motivate them to teach effectively and go extra miles	2.76	0.092	Moderate
4 Prompt payment and fair remuneration of salaries can ginger staff into working to achieve good service delivery	3.42	0.359	High
5 Periodic wellness checks on staff can give them a sense of belonging and as well motivate them to be diligent	2.60	0.212	Moderate
6 Respect for teachers by administrative staff can create a friendly relationship between them for effective teaching / leaning.	3.48	0.359	High
7 Cooperation of staff in supervision during examination will broaden their horizon of learning	1.94	0.377	Very low
Aggregate	2.8	0.149	Moderate

*Mean: 1.0-2.0 = Very Low Extent; 2.1-2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5-2.99 = Moderate Extent; 3.0-3.49 = High Extent; and 3.5-4.0 = Very High Extent

Table 1 showed the Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Motivation of teachers influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. the result which yielded an The aggregate mean of 2.8 with a standard deviation of 0.149 in Table 3 indicates that the motivation of teachers is perceived at a moderate extent influence effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This suggests a balanced yet nuanced view on the role of teacher's motivation in educational management.

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Training/development of teachers influence effective administration public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

S/N	Training/development of teachers for effective administration	Mean	St.Dev	Decision
1	Staff give quality and efficient transmission of their duties when they are given much workloads and no time for planning and teaching	1.37	0.317	Very low
2	Teaching - staff teach more efficient and effortlessly when they are provided with the required instructional materials	3.29	0.21	High
3	Staff requires more skills for quality services when they are given continuing education and personal life long expansion.	3.04	0.17	High
	Aggregate	2.57	0.062	moderate

*Mean: 1.0-2.0 = Very Low Extent; 2.1-2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5-2.99 = Moderate Extent; 3.0-3.49 = High Extent; and 3.5-4.0 = Very High Extent

Table 2 Summarized the mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Training/development of teachers for effective administration influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. the analysis revealed The aggregate mean of 2.57 and a low standard deviation of 0.062 in Table 4 suggest a moderate overall perception regarding the impact of teachers training and development on the effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This indicates a recognition of the importance of continued education and provision of instructional materials for enhancing teaching efficiency, though not at an extensively high level

Table 3: Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Communication Strategies influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

S/N	Principals-teacher Communication Strategies	Mean	St.Dev	Decision
1	Internet can be a great constraint to principals-teachers communication in a school premises	3.07	0.257	Very low
2	Poor internet connection delay in information processing which affect effective administration in decision making process	3.67	0.357	High
	Aggregate	3.37	0.234	high

*Mean: 1.0-2.0 = Very Low Extent; 2.1-2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5-2.99 = Moderate Extent; 3.0-3.49 = High Extent; and 3.5-4.0 = Very High Extent

In Table 3, the aggregate mean of 3.37 with a standard deviation of 0.234 suggests that communication strategies, particularly useful to internet use and connectivity, are perceived as highly significant in their impact on the effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This high rating indicates a strong consensus on the importance of reliable internet for timely information processing and decision-making in school administration

Table 4: Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the extent Motivation of Staff significantly correlates with Effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

		Effective management	Motivation of Staff
Effective management	Pearson Correlation	1	.321
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.024
	N	384	384
Motivation of Staff	Pearson Correlation	.321	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	
	N	384	384

*R² = 0.1030

In Table 4, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .321 between staff motivation and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, demonstrates a low to moderate positive correlation. This indicates that there is a relationship between how teachers are motivated and the effectiveness of school management, but it's not a strong one. The significance value (Sig.) of .024 is below the conventional threshold of .05, confirming the statistical significance of this correlation. However, the R² value of 0.1030 suggests that staff motivation accounts for approximately 10.30% of the variance in effective management. This implies that while motivation of staff is a factor in school management effectiveness, it is one of several contributing elements, and not the dominant influencer.

Table 5: Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the extent Training/ development of staff for effective administration significantly correlates with Effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

Effective	Training/ development of	management	staff for	effective
			administration	
Effective management	Pearson	1	.447	
	Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	
	N	384	384	
Training/ development of staff for effective administration	Pearson	.447	1	
	Correlation	.002		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	384	384	

*R² = 0.1998

In Table 5, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .447 indicates a moderate positive correlation between training/development of staff for effective administration and the effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This correlation suggests that as the training and development of staff improve, there is a corresponding moderate increase in the effectiveness of school management. The significance level (Sig.) of .002, which is significantly below the standard threshold of .05, reinforces the statistical significance of this relationship. The R² value of 0.1998 means that about 19.98% of the variance in the effectiveness of school management can be explained by the training and development activities for staff. This finding highlights the substantial role that staff training and development play in enhancing the management efficiency of schools.

Table 6: Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the extent communication strategies significantly correlates with Effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

		Effective	communication
		management	strategies
Effective management	Pearson	1	.601
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	384	384

communication strategies	Pearson	.601	1
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	384	384

*R² = 0.3612

In Table 6, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .601 between communication strategies and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, signifies a strong positive correlation. This indicates a robust relationship where improvements in communication strategies are closely associated with enhancements in the effectiveness of school management. The significance level (Sig.) of .000, which is well below the standard alpha level of .05, strongly confirms the statistical significance of this correlation. Additionally, the R² value of 0.3612 implies that approximately 36.12% of the variance in the effectiveness of school management can be attributed to the quality and effectiveness of communication strategies. This underscores the critical importance of communication in the administration and management of educational institutions.

Discussion

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .321 between staff motivation and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, demonstrates a low to moderate positive correlation. This indicated that there is a relationship between how teachers are motivated and the effectiveness of school management, but it's not a strong one. The significance value (Sig.) of .024 is below the conventional threshold of .05, confirmed the statistical significance of this correlation. However, the R² value of 0.1030 suggests that staff motivation accounts for approximately 10.30% of the variance in effective management. This implies that while motivation of staff is a factor in school management effectiveness, it is one of several contributing elements, and not the dominant influenced.

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .447 indicated a moderate positive correlation between training/development of teachers for effective administration and the effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This correlation suggested that as the training and development of teachers improved, there is a corresponding moderate increase in the effectiveness of school management. The significance level (Sig.) of .002, which is significantly below the standard threshold of .05, reinforces the statistical significance of this relationship. The R² value of 0.1998 means that about 19.98% of the variance in the effectiveness of school management can be explained by the training and development activities for staff. This finding highlighted the substantial role that staff training and development play in enhancing the management efficiency of schools. Nwosu &

Chukwuere (2017) findings was opposite to this study, the majority of principals and school board members (SBMS) did not seem to have received school board training. It also revealed lack of adherence to policies such as offering training to SBMS in order for them to perform their roles and responsibilities effectively.

Ayeni & Akinola (2020) findings indicated significant relationship between principals' communication strategies and teachers' productivity ($r = 0.680, p < 0.05$) was poor internet connection which is in line with this study findings. Lack of modern communication facilities to enhance teacher's productivity. This high rating indicates a strong consensus on the importance of reliable internet for timely information processing and decision-making in school administration. Oyugi & Gogo (2018). Findings showed otherwise because there was no information about the influence while Ekechukwu & Ifeanyi (2021) results revealed positive outcomes for effective communication, collective decision making, compliance to staff code of conduct with this study. It was streamline to teachers and principals' communication. This study results revealed that, Communication Strategies have the aggregate mean of 3.37 with a standard deviation of 0.234 suggested that communication strategies, particularly internet use and connectivity, are perceived as highly significant in their impact on the effective management of public secondary schools.

Kindika (2009) finding is at identical with the study who Opined that level of discipline in secondary schools' administration rarely discussed implementation of rules and regulations to students hence there are poor chances of communication. In effective communication results in conflict, chaos, misunderstanding and lack of confidence in school administration. Factors such as individual communication skills promoted effective communication whereas barriers to interpersonal communication hindered effective communication, and the finding is at variance with Omemu (2017) on the study of Communication Strategies the aggregate mean of 3.37 with a standard deviation of 0.234 suggested that communication strategies, particularly related to internet use and connectivity, are perceived as highly significant in their impact on the effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. This high rating indicated a strong consensus on the importance of reliable internet for timely information processing and decision-making in school administration. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .601 between communication strategies and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, signified a strong positive correlation. This indicated a robust relationship where improvements in communication strategies are closely associated with enhancements in the effectiveness of school management. The significance level (Sig.) of .000, which is well below the standard alpha level of .05, strongly confirmed the statistical significance of this correlation. Additionally, the R^2 value of 0.3612 implies that approximately 36.12% of the variance in the effectiveness of school management can be attributed to the quality and effectiveness of communication strategies. This underscores the critical importance of communication in the administration and management of educational institutions.

Conclusion

The interplay of motivation, communication, and training is integral to the administrative effectiveness of secondary schools in Obio/Akpor. Motivation alone shows a modest correlation with effective management, it remains an essential component of a supportive school environment. Given the moderate

correlation between training and effective management, it is imperative to continuously invest in the professional development of principals and teachers. The strong positive correlation between communication strategies and effective management highlights the need for robust communication systems. Schools should establish clear communication channels, utilize technology to facilitate real-time information sharing, and foster an open dialogue among all stakeholders. Regular feedback sessions and parent-teacher meetings can further enhance transparency and collaboration. Finally, the study recommended among others that the principals should sustain the use of motivation, communication and training of teachers as part of teaching and learning in secondary schools

Recommendation Motivation;

1. The government should establish both intrinsic and extrinsic reward systems to recognize and celebrate the achievements of teachers and students. **Training/ development**
2. The government and the minister of education should offer career advancement opportunities, such as promotions and additional responsibilities, to motivate teachers.
3. The principals should encourage teachers to pursue higher qualifications and certifications by providing financial support or study leave.

Communication Channels

4. The school management should implement communication tools such as group chats, video conferencing, and online forums to facilitate real-time communication among stakeholders.
5. The school principals should use social media and the school website to keep the school community updated and engaged with school activities.
6. The government should create an open-door policy where teachers and students feel comfortable sharing their ideas and concerns with the school administration.

References

- Ayeni, A.J., & Akinola, O.B., (2020) Organizational communication and teacher's productivity in secondary schools in Ondo State. Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(17), 35-52.
- Kindika, J. N. (2009). Effectiveness of Communication on students discipline in secondary schools in Kenya *Educational Research and Review*, 4(5), 252-259.
- Muheeb, R. (2014) Basic motivation strategies and teacher performance in Somolo Local government Area of Lagos State. Bachelor of Education Degree of University of Lagos
- Nkwoh, J. (2016). Analysis of administrative roles of principals in private Secondary school in Abia Education Zone of Abia State. *Journal of Educational Administration* 2(1), 33-41.

- Okolie, C. R, Akulue, N.M, Anaedu, N.F. & Amangbo, U.N.M (2022). Effectiveness of administrative strategies used by principals in handling disciplinary problems in Anambra State Public secondary schools. COOU Journal of Education Research, 7(1), 399-410.
- Okoroma, N.S (2016). Administrative abilities of male and female principals and goals achievement in Nigerian public secondary schools. Journal of culture, society and development, 20(2), 6-15.
- Onubuleze, F. K & Cletus, A. (2023). Strategies adopted by principals in the management of School plant in Secondary Schools in Enugu State. Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies, 5(1), 439-448.
- Onuorah, H.C & Eziamaka, C.N(2021). Principals' planning strategies for school improvement and quality assurance in secondary schools in Awka Education zone. Sapientia foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies (SFJESGS) ,3(1), 85-95.
- Omemu, F., (2017). Relationship between principals' administrative strategies and students. Disciplinary problems in secondary school, Bayelsa State. Journal of Education and practice, 18(5), 223-288.
- Omemu,F., 2017). Relationship between principal administrative strategies and students' disciplinary problems in secondary schools, Bayelsa State. Journal of Education and Practice, 8(5), 100-104.
- Pinder, C.C (2018). Work motivation in organizational behaviour. New York. Psychology Press
- Re ém, Y. (2016). Motivating public school employees: An application Oriented Analysis of possibilities and practical tools Hietie School of governance, working paper